

THE MAIN MOTIVES OF BORIS PASTERNAK'S LYRICS

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Abstract. Boris Pasternak (1890-1960) was one of the most outstanding poets of Russian literature of the 20th century, also known as a novelist, translator and musicologist. Pasternak's lyricism is characterized by its comprehensive meaning, deep thinking and richness of literary expressions. His poetry not only reflects the problems of his time, but also seeks answers to the general existential problems of man. Pasternak's lyrics center on themes such as division, exploration, spiritual freedom, and spiritual suffering. In this article, we will try to analyze in detail the main motives of Pasternak's lyrics and their artistic expression.

Keywords: Boris Pasternak, lyric, motif, poetry, literature, exploration.

ОСНОВНЫЕ МОТИВЫ ЛИРИКИ БОРИСА ПАСТЕРНАКА

Аннотация. Борис Пастернак (1890-1960) - один из самых выдающихся поэтов русской литературы XX века, известный также как прозаик, переводчик и музыковед. Лирика Пастернака отличается всеобъемлющим смыслом, глубиной мышления и богатством литературных выражений. Его поэзия не только отражает проблемы своего времени, но и ищет ответы на общие экзистенциальные проблемы человека. Лирика Пастернака сосредоточена на таких темах, как разделение, исследование, духовная свобода и духовное страдание. В этой статье мы попытаемся подробно проанализировать основные мотивы лирики Пастернака и их художественное выражение.

Ключевые слова: Борис Пастернак, лирика, мотив, поэзия, литература, исследование.

Link between man and nature

An important theme in Pasternak's lyrical works is the relationship between nature and man. Nature, for the poet, is portrayed not only as the outside world, but as part of the human soul. Pasternak connects nature with his passions, suffering and dreams. Nature reflects balance and peace in his poems, as well as inner exploration.

In the poetry of the poet, such as winter autumn, changes in nature are often compared with personal circumstances, mental states.

The connection between nature and man creates a kind of poetic symbolism in the poet's poetic language. When nature is expressed Pasternak, it becomes a force that reflects the inner world of man.

Social and political themes

Pasternak's lyrical works also reflect tensions over the political atmosphere of the Soviet era. In the poet's poetry, especially the contradictions between totalitarianism and human freedom are often explored. Pasternak reworked the political pressure of the Soviet Union and the need for freedom in his works. While he maintained a unique critical spirit in his works, many of his works focused on the mental state of Man and his inner quest.

Boris Pasternak's novel "Doctor Zhivago" reflects not only the inner world of man, but also the social and political problems of his time. In his poems, too, Pasternak describes how humanity affects general historical processes while exploring the social condition of people.

Mental suffering and exploration

One of the main motives in Pasternak's poetry is the spiritual torment and inner search of a person. The poet deeply reflects on the complexity of life, the search for the self of a person and the meaning of existence. His poetry has always been aimed at clarifying the inner state of a person and his spiritual searches. Pasternak's poems often incorporate motifs of suffering, exploration, despair, and the need for freedom.

In his poetry, in works such as "the first step", the poet deeply covered the themes of the search for the inner world of Man and the search for spiritual liberation. Nature, people's relationships and their search – all this is seen as an image of spiritual search in Pasternak's lyrical works.

Love and romanticism

A special place in the lyrical poetry of Boris Pasternak is occupied by the motive of love.

The poet describes the spiritual freedom of a person through love, his inner world and his aspirations for heights. Love, for Pasternak, is not only associated with personal feelings, but is seen as a spiritually exalting force in a person's life.

In Pasternak's poems about love, in particular, works such as "on Love", love manifests itself as a factor in the formation of a person's spiritual presence. Love for Pasternak lyricism is always associated with perfection, elevation and the finding of a person himself. Through love, he calls on a person to achieve spiritual freedom, harmony with the outside world.

Homeland and nation issues

Boris Pasternak's lyrics reflect love for his nationality and Homeland. In his poetic works, the poet describes his devotion to his people, his historical and cultural identity.

For Pasternak, the homeland is not only a geographical area, but also a spiritual and cultural home of a person, associated with his ancestors.

In his poetic works, the poet tries to describe the values of his homeland, the pain and joy of his people. Pasternak's poems on the theme of "Fatherland" show his patriotism, feeling the pain of his nation.

Creativity and art

Pasternak's lyricism also places a strong emphasis on the importance of creativity and art.

The poet's attitude towards art is in keeping with his vision of life. Through creativity, Pasternak tries to reflect the inner world of man, his connection with nature, his love and hopes. In poetry, the purpose of creativity is shown as to reveal the inner world of a person, to help him find his place in life.

The themes of art and creation in Pasternak's poetry also shed light on his attitudes towards life. The poet views art not only as a transforming force of people, but also as a means of introducing a person to his inner world, exalting his existence.

Tabriz and awareness

Pasternak's poetry uses many figurative images, metaphors. Variable, ambiguous, non-stationary images are central to his poems. Pasternak's poetics often reflect uncertainty, complexity, and variability. This makes his poetry richer and more imaginative.

Conclusion

Boris Pasternak's lyrical works are characterized by their deep meaning, artistic richness and focus on the study of universal problems regarding humanity. His poetry covers the themes of nature and man, love and exploration, political criticism, and spiritual freedom. Pasternak's lyrics deal not only with the literary traditions of his time, but also with the general moral and spiritual state of mankind, leaving each reader with his own deep and meaningful conclusions.

Through the poet's poems, his spiritual quest and his high spirituality, we are seen as a window to help us realize the most glorious values and problems of humanity.

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